

Green Materials for Sustainable Development

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Abstract

The use of Green materials has evolved as a major challenge with industrialisation. In the 21st century, it has remained an issue for the scientists, economists, industrialists and engineers for the substantial development, preservation of material, health concerns and economic loss. Environmentally friendly materials have attracted great attention to the researchers. Recent studies have proven that compounds obtained from plant extracts with biodegradable, environmentally accommodative, relatively cheap, and no harmful features as the most perfect approach to tackling the problem. Plant extracts are used as green corrosion inhibitors (GCIs) for the metals. In addition, porous carbon is used as supercapacitor electrode material. This talk discusses the plant extracts for the corrosion protection of metals such as mild steel, copper. Similarly, porous carbon prepared from *Lantana camara* bark for the supercapacitor electrode. Moreover, metal oxide/ polyaniline – biomass composite electrodes for the high performance supercapacitors is discussed.

Keywords: *corrosion inhibitor, green materials, lantana camara, polyaniline, supercapacitor*